

Chirped surface gratings on azopolymers from digital holographic photomorphing

Francesco Reda¹,^{a,*} Fabio Borbone¹,^b Marcella Salvatore¹,^a
and Stefano L. Oscurato¹,^{a,*}

^aUniversity of Naples "Federico II", Complesso Universitario di Monte Sant'Angelo,
Physics Department "E. Pancini", Naples, Italy

^bUniversity of Naples "Federico II", Complesso Universitario di Monte Sant'Angelo,
Department of Chemical Sciences, Naples, Italy

ABSTRACT. Azomaterials are a powerful class of photoactive materials capable of surface morphing under structured light, enabling fully reprogrammable micro-optical elements. We demonstrate the fabrication and dynamic reconfiguration of linearly chirped diffraction gratings via azopolymer-based photomorphing using digital holographic lithography. This method allows continuous control over the spatial distribution of the grating vectors, encoding a wide range of periodicities within a single exposure, an achievement typically hampered by conventional two-beam interference techniques. Real-time monitoring of diffraction efficiency also boosts direct optimization of lithographic parameters, ensuring agreement with theoretical predictions of scalar diffraction theory. The full reconfigurability of the azopolymer surface also allows dynamic tuning of the diffraction orders, including both the angular and spectral distribution as well as the power ratio of the diffracted light. These capabilities further establish our approach as a versatile platform for advancing azopolymer-based reconfigurable diffractive optics.

© The Authors. Published by SPIE under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. Distribution or reproduction of this work in whole or in part requires full attribution of the original publication, including its DOI. [DOI: [10.1117/1.JOM.5.2.024002](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JOM.5.2.024002)]

Keywords: chirped surface relief gratings; digital photolithography; azomaterial photopatterning; reprogrammable diffractive optical elements; computer-generated holography

Paper 25022G received Mar. 10, 2025; revised May 29, 2025; accepted May 30, 2025; published Jun. 17, 2025.

1 Introduction

Diffraction gratings are among the earliest reported diffractive optical elements¹ and have played a fundamental role in the development of modern optical technologies. These optical components typically consist of a periodic array of grooves etched on a substrate, forming a structured surface that modulates light.² The periodicity of the surface geometry results in discrete diffraction orders, enabling applications such as wavelength separation and beam splitting.³ Because the optical functionality of a transmissive surface relief grating is determined by the groove parameters, including spacing, depth, and profile shape, and by the refractive index of the grating material, various grating geometries have been proposed. These include chirped gratings, in which the periodicity varies continuously across the surface.^{2,4} This spatial variation of groove spacing in these diffractive elements produces broad diffraction angles, enabling more advanced optical functionalities, such as the design of optical bandpass filters,^{5,6} beam steering and shaping,⁷⁻⁹ and improved spectrometer performance.¹⁰⁻¹² Accurate design and implementation of the

*Address all correspondence to Francesco Reda, francesco.reda@unina.it, Stefano L. Oscurato, stefanoluigi.oscurato@unina.it

aperiodic grating profile are essential to ensure their optimal performance, making the fabrication of these components a critical factor.¹³

Typically, surface relief gratings, similar to those forming a chirped diffraction grating, are fabricated using photolithography,¹⁴ mechanical ruling,¹⁵ or holographic exposure methods.¹⁶ These conventional fabrication methods face several limitations, especially when targeting post-fabrication changes to the device geometry, which is typically frozen after fabrication, hampering the applicability of the obtained diffraction gratings in reprogrammable optical devices.¹⁷

Amorphous materials containing azobenzene molecules are emerging as promising photomorphable systems for lithographic applications, enabling direct and reversible surface patterning by simple optical illumination.^{18,19} Photoinduced surface morphing is driven by the cyclic *trans*–*cis* photoisomerization of the embedded azobenzene units upon exposure to spatially modulated UV and visible light fields.²⁰ The molecular-scale movement of the azobenzene molecules leads to the appearance of light-induced stress in the host material, which initiates reversible surface mass migration.^{21–23} This allows the all-optical fabrication of reconfigurable diffractive optical elements where surface topographies can be dynamically modified.^{24–26} The fabrication of periodic surface relief gratings using this technique has been successfully demonstrated using various illumination schemes, including sinusoidal intensity or polarization patterns generated by the interference of two coherent laser beams.^{26–32} Although sequential multiple exposures have enabled more complex designs,^{33–36} achieving a continuous and broad range of grating periodicities required for chirped grating design remains challenging and requires sophisticated optical configurations.³⁷ To overcome these limitations, digital holography techniques have been employed to shape light and enable complex surface designs.³⁸ Computer-generated holograms offer a versatile and digitally programmable method for patterning azopolymer surfaces, leveraging spatial light modulators (SLMs) to generate arbitrarily structured light fields. By encoding polarization^{39–41} or intensity variations^{42–44} into the projected illumination, this method allows the fabrication of diffraction gratings with precisely controlled grating vector orientations and magnitudes and extends to the fabrication of reprogrammable diffractive components, including chirped gratings,⁴⁵ diffractive lenses,⁴⁶ and holographic projectors.⁴⁴

In this paper, we report the fabrication of linearly chirped diffraction gratings on an azobenzene-containing polymer using digital holographic photopatterning. Although this grating geometry has recently been demonstrated in azopolymers using structured polarization fields generated by an SLM,⁴⁵ we show that precise engineering of a holographic intensity pattern allows us to compensate for spurious amplitude modulation arising from variations in the contrast of the writing hologram at different periodicities. In addition, we describe the diffraction behavior using a full scalar theory approach, extending a model we previously developed for general periodic sinusoidal-like surface relief gratings to the accurate analysis of the diffraction of chirped surface gratings.^{47,48} This theoretical framework closely aligns with experimental results, providing a robust predictive tool for optimizing grating design and its diffraction efficiency, even in real time. Finally, we demonstrate that an existing grating can be completely reshaped to fabricate a new chirped grating with a different grating vector distribution on the same surface area. Our results underscore the potential of digital holographic photomorphing for directly fabricating operational and fully reprogrammable diffractive optics on azopolymers.

2 From Discrete to the Continuously Varying Grating Vectors of Chirped Gratings

To highlight the fundamental aspects of chirped gratings and their diffraction properties, we briefly describe the design principles of linear chirped gratings. Because a periodic diffraction grating consists of a repeating structure, it can be characterized not only in real space by its period but also in terms of its spatial frequency components. The grating vector \vec{g} provides a framework for describing gratings in reciprocal space, which facilitates the analysis of their optical behavior.⁴⁹ For a one-dimensional periodic grating with periodicity Λ , the grating vector \vec{g} lies in the plane of the grating and it is expressed as $\vec{g} = 2\pi/\Lambda \cdot \hat{n}$, where \hat{n} is a unit vector perpendicular to the grooves. In the context of periodic or multiplexed gratings, the structure can be represented by a discrete set of grating vectors, each corresponding to a particular grating component.⁵⁰ If the period varies along a given direction, the grating structure becomes aperiodic.

Fig. 1 Surface profile of a *p*-chirped surface relief grating (a) and a *q*-chirped surface relief grating (b). The plots on the right show the grating periodicity $\Lambda(x)$ and the grating vector magnitude $g(x)$ as functions of the lateral position, normalized by the total grating length, L . The gray-shaded region under the curve represents the integral function $G(x)$, which defines the modulation characteristics according to the chirped grating equation.

Such structures, known as *chirped gratings*, are characterized by a continuous spatial variation of the grating vector within a desired range.² The surface profile $h(x, y)$ of a surface relief chirped grating can be defined as

$$h(x, y) = \frac{\Delta h}{2} [1 + \sin(G(x))] = \frac{\Delta h}{2} \left[1 + \sin \left(\int_0^x g(x) dx \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where (x, y) are the spatial coordinates in the plane of the grating and Δh represents the grating modulation depth, as shown in Fig. 1. The function $G(x)$ is the integral of the local grating vector magnitude $g(x) = 2\pi/\Lambda(x)$, which accounts for the local grating periodicity $\Lambda(x)$.^{7,8} Conventionally, there are two types of linearly chirped gratings, depending on the way the period varies spatially. For *p-chirped* gratings with lateral length L , the period $\Lambda(x)$ varies linearly: $\Lambda(x) = \Lambda_1 + \frac{\Lambda_2 - \Lambda_1}{L}x$, where Λ_1 and Λ_2 correspond to the smallest and largest periodicities of the grating, respectively. The center of the grating is, without loss of generality, located at $x = L/2$. Given the inverse relationship between the period and the grating vector, a linear variation of $\Lambda(x)$ leads to a nonlinear variation of the grating vector in reciprocal space, resulting in a nonlinear decrease of $g(x)$. This case is illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

Conversely, for *q-chirped* gratings, the magnitude of the grating vector varies linearly in reciprocal space, and the grating can be designed directly in reciprocal space by its initial and final grating vectors, $g_1 = 2\pi/\Lambda_1$ and $g_2 = 2\pi/\Lambda_2$. This results in a nonlinear variation of the local period when mapped back to real space, as shown in Fig. 1(b). These examples highlight a fundamental property of chirped gratings: they are characterized by a continuously varying spectrum of grating vectors rather than a discrete set. As a result, they cannot be decomposed or synthesized by a finite superposition of sinusoidal functions. This is particularly important when comparing chirped gratings to optical Fourier surfaces, which rely on such decompositions.^{24,50} Consequently, the fabrication of surface relief chirped gratings requires appropriate lithographic techniques to ensure their proper implementation in functional optical components. This challenge becomes even more critical when working with azomaterials, as the conventional two-beam interference sequential approach is no longer suitable.

3 Optimized Fabrication of Linearly Chirped Gratings on Azopolymers

Our experimental setup allows the generation of a holographic intensity pattern on the surface of an amorphous azopolymer film using a computer-generated hologram scheme. Because the surface design is digitally controlled and the patterning is performed in a single all-optical

Fig. 2 (a) Schematic representation of the digital lithography setup used for azopolymer photo-morphing, illustrating the optical configuration employed to generate and project holographic patterns onto the azopolymer surface. (b) Step-by-step inscription process of a chirped surface relief grating: (i) a digitally encoded grayscale image representing the target holographic pattern and (ii) a brightfield microscopy image of the pristine azopolymer surface before exposure. The inset displays the chemical structure of the azopolymer material used in this study; (iii) an experimentally generated holographic intensity pattern projected onto the azopolymer film during inscription and (iv) a brightfield microscopy image of the azopolymer surface after exposure, revealing the formation of a chirped surface relief grating.

illumination step, this approach facilitates the straightforward fabrication of chirped diffraction gratings that contain all the necessary grating components. As shown in Fig. 2(a), a linearly polarized laser beam (from a Calyps-Cobolt) at a wavelength of 491 nm is used as the main illumination source. After passing through a beam expander, the laser beam is phase-modulated by a reflective spatial light modulator (SLM, Pluto 2.1-Holoeye) with a pixel size of $\Delta = 8 \mu\text{m}$. After modulation, the beam is propagated through a $4f$ optical system consisting of two lenses (L_1 and L_2) with focal lengths of $f_1 = 300 \text{ mm}$ and $f_2 = 175 \text{ mm}$, respectively. This projection system generates a scaled version of the modulated field (SLM plane) at the back focal plane of an infinity-corrected microscope objective. The microscope objective, with a numerical aperture of $\text{NA} = 0.55$ and a $\times 50$ magnification, focuses the structured illumination onto the azopolymer film.

The optical system is designed to maximize spatial resolution in the hologram reconstruction plane. The sample position is precisely controlled by an $x - y - z$ translation stage. For visual inspection and precise focusing of the holographic light pattern on the material surface, a 90:10 beam splitter (BS) is placed in the light path. This beam splitter directs the retroreflected light from the surface, which is recollimated by the objective, to a tube lens (TL). This forms an image of the holographic pattern in its second focal plane, where a CCD camera (Kiralux-Thorlabs) is positioned to capture the image. During exposure, an additional 405-nm diode laser illuminates the sample from the substrate side. This circularly polarized laser beam is used at different intensity levels depending on the intended function.^{24,33} First, it is used to accelerate the patterning process (at 0.5 W/cm^2) or to erase previously inscribed surface structures (at 1 W/cm^2) without significant material degradation. These power levels were selected according to the detailed empirical characterization of the influence of the assisting beam power on the relief formation dynamics, reported in our previous work.^{24,44} An additional white LED light source is employed as a back-illumination source during the patterning process.

To show the tuning and optimization capabilities of our holographic configuration, the intensity pattern $I(x, y)$ to be projected onto the sample is first designed to follow a p -chirped grating

distribution. The grating parameters are set considering the characteristics of our setup. The smallest periodicity ($\Lambda_1 = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$) was chosen to avoid low-contrast light patterns that could result from approaching the resolution limit of the optical system.⁴² The largest periodicity ($\Lambda_2 = 8.5 \mu\text{m}$) ensures a sufficiently wide chirp range. The lateral size of $L = 150 \mu\text{m}$ closely matches the maximum area that can be effectively illuminated by the holographic pattern within the field of view of our experimental configuration.⁴⁴ These parameters for chirp range and lateral size were selected to ensure high-fidelity pattern inscription within the effective resolution limit of the setup while maximizing the patterned area. To implement this light pattern experimentally, a digital representation of $I(x, y)$ is generated by sampling the functional dependence described by Eq. (1) into a pixelated grayscale image with a size of 1080×1080 pixels, equal to the resolution of the SLM. Each pixel in the target image corresponds to a physical dimension of $0.39 \mu\text{m}$ on the sample, as determined by prior system calibration.⁴² This digital image representing the target light distribution is shown in Fig. 2(bi). The phase mask (kinoform) for the SLM is generated using an iterative Fourier transform algorithm with the target image as input. The mixed region amplitude freedom algorithm implemented in MATLAB was used.⁵¹

To fabricate reprogrammable chirped surface relief gratings, an azopolymer was synthesized via radical polymerization of (E)-2-(4-((4-methoxyphenyl) diazenyl) phenoxy) ethyl acrylate, as previously reported. The SRG film was prepared by spin-coating a filtered ($0.2 \mu\text{m}$ PTFE) 140 mg/mL solution of the polymer in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane onto a glass coverslip at 300 rpm for 4 min, resulting in a film thickness of $1.7 \mu\text{m}$. The chemical structure of the azopolymer and the brightfield image of the surface before patterning are shown in Fig. 2(bii). The experimental intensity pattern $I(x, y)$ projected on the azopolymer surface is shown in Fig. 2(biii). To reduce the effect of high speckle noise contrast associated with iterative Fourier transform algorithms, the holographic illumination over the azopolymer surface is the result of the time average of 1000 holographic patterns generated from independently computed kinoforms, according to the established procedure described in our previous works.^{24,38} The SLM refresh rate is set to 60 Hz, which is the maximum value allowed by our device. This enables the entire sequence of independently evaluated kinoforms to be displayed in ~ 17 s. Such a timescale is lower than the typical surface relief formation time on the azopolymer surface. However, the selected number of independent kinoform is already sufficient to significantly reduce speckle-related surface roughness, allowing uniform patterns suitable for high-fidelity lithography. An average intensity of 12.0 W/cm^2 is used for azopolymer photopatterning, along with circular polarization achieved by a quarter waveplate (QWP) placed before the objective. During exposure to the holographic pattern, the polymer flows from the high-intensity region to the dark areas and directly forms a stable surface relief pattern $h(x, y, t)$ that replicates the lateral geometry of the chirped illumination intensity, as shown in Fig. 2(biv). Under our illumination conditions, the exposure time t influences the total relief modulation depth Δh , which increases approximately linearly with the exposure time. This allows us to fully implement the geometry described in Eq. (1) by properly spatially tuning the exposure dose.

Figure 3(a) shows the image of the reconstructed holographic pattern obtained by averaging 1000 holographic frames collected by the CCD. This image was acquired at the working distance of the microscope objective by placing a mirror at the sample plane. Averaging along the columns of the experimental image reveals the corresponding holographic profile, highlighting a key mismatch with respect to the target. Smaller light features, corresponding to the smallest local periodicity, exhibit reduced contrast as they approach the diffraction limit of the setup.⁴² This results in spurious amplitude modulation across the surface of the chirped grating when the holographic pattern is used for azopolymer photomorphing. Such a deviation represents a strong mismatch with respect to the ideal grating design, which prescribes a uniform groove amplitude. To quantify this effect, we performed a morphological characterization of the azopolymer surface after the inscription of the p -chirped grating. Figure 3(b) shows the topography of the grating surface obtained using an atomic force microscope (AFM, Alpha RS300–WITec). The AFM was operated in tapping mode using tips (Arrow FM–Nano World) with a nominal radius of curvature of ~ 10 nm. The corresponding profile, averaged along the groove direction, confirms the propagation of the nonuniform amplitude in the optical pattern to the final surface modulation. The measurement was performed over an area of $50 \times 140 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a lateral resolution of 100 nm. The inscription of the surface relief geometry was achieved by exposing the azopolymer film

Fig. 3 (a) Experimentally generated holographic pattern used for the inscription of chirped surface relief gratings. The plot compares the measured illumination intensity profile (solid blue line) with the target intensity distribution (dashed gray line). (b) Atomic force microscopy (AFM) micrograph of the inscribed chirped grating (top) and the corresponding averaged height profile along the x -direction (bottom), demonstrating the spatial variation of the grating modulation.

to the holographic pattern sequence for 60 s, resulting in an average groove modulation depth of $\Delta h = 0.50 \mu\text{m}$ with a standard deviation of $0.11 \mu\text{m}$. Unlike other approaches where the local contrast is inherently tied to the optical setup, our method provides the flexibility to digitally adjust the light field, ensuring that deviations from the ideal profile can be systematically addressed. This can be done by properly redefining the target image entering the kinoform calculation, allowing any necessary correction to be incorporated during the hologram design, even point by point. To determine the appropriate correction function, we first analyzed the local contrast $\mathcal{C}(x_i)$ of the experimentally reconstructed holographic pattern by identifying the local intensity minima (I_{\min}^i) and the local intensity maxima (I_{\max}^i) along the normalized holographic profile shown in Fig. 3(a).

The contrast at each position was then calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum intensity values, $\mathcal{C}(x_i) = I_{\max}^i - I_{\min}^i$, and plotted as a function of the discrete lateral coordinate x_i , obtained as the midpoint between the position of the i 'th maxima and the position of the i 'th minima of the profile. The resulting plot is shown in Fig. 4(a), which highlights an approximately linearly increasing contrast of the hologram over the irradiated area. To obtain an analytical description of this spatial dependence, we performed a linear fit of the contrast profile, which allowed us to retrieve the correction function. This was then used to modify the digital target image of the hologram to compensate for the observed intensity contrast variations. By implementing the corrected hologram, a uniform light modulation amplitude was achieved over the entire exposed area, as shown in both the contrast plot and the experimental light modulation profile in Fig. 4(a). This directly translates into a p -chirped grating inscription with uniform modulation depth across the surface, as shown in the AFM image in Fig. 4(b). The exposure time of 75 s was used to achieve an average modulation depth ($\Delta h = 0.53 \mu\text{m}$ in this case) comparable to the structure previously obtained without contrast correction. The slower inscription dynamics is related to the lower intensity in the holographic image due to the correction process. Importantly, the AFM profile shows a reduced standard deviation of $0.03 \mu\text{m}$ for the modulation depth across the grating.

4 Real-Time Diffraction Characterization and Surface Reprogrammability

The diffraction pattern of the surface chirped gratings can be theoretically modeled by considering the optical path differences encountered by a probe plane wave of wavelength λ as it propagates orthogonally through the structured material layer, which has a homogeneous refractive

Fig. 4 (a) Evolution of the local contrast of the holographic pattern before (gray points) and after (blue points) the contrast correction. The correction function was derived from a linear fit (red dashed line) of the initial contrast distribution, characterized by a best-fit slope of $1.8 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and an intercept of 0.35. The bottom plot shows the corrected intensity profile, exhibiting a more uniform modulation across the spatial extent. (b) Atomic force microscopy (AFM) micrograph of the fabricated chirped surface relief grating after contrast correction (top) and the corresponding average height profile along the x -direction (bottom), confirming the improved uniformity of the grating modulation.

index n . Diffraction occurs due to the phase delay induced by the varying surface height of the chirped grating with respect to the surrounding medium, assumed to be air.³³ For a structured surface exhibiting a morphological modulation $h(x, y)$ described by Eq. (1), its optical functionality can be characterized by a pure complex transmission function given by⁴⁹

$$t(x, y) = \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (n - 1) h(x, y) \right]. \quad (2)$$

In a scalar approximation, the far-field diffraction intensity pattern $I(k_x)$ of this phase-only diffractive optical element can be evaluated using Fraunhofer diffraction, which states that the far-field optical field $E(k_x)$ is proportional to the Fourier transform of the transmission function of the surface in the modulation plane.^{49,52} Here, $k_x = 2\pi\lambda^{-1} \sin(\theta)$ represents the spatial frequencies related to far-field coordinates, expressed as a function of the polar coordinate θ .⁴⁹ Applying the Jacobi-Anger identity,⁵³ the transmission $t(x, y)$ can be expanded in terms of Bessel functions of the first kind J_m of order m , leading to^{47,48}

$$I(k_x) \propto \left| \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_m \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) \int_{-\frac{\Lambda}{2}}^{\frac{\Lambda}{2}} e^{i(mG(x) - k_x x)} dx \right|^2 = \left| \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} J_m \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \right) F(k_x) \right|^2. \quad (3)$$

In this equation, the sum indexed by m represents the different diffraction orders produced by the grating. Each order corresponds to a particular angular direction in which the light is diffracted. The square modulus of each Bessel function J_m in Eq. (3) quantifies the fraction of energy present in each diffraction order and allows the definition of the diffraction efficiency η_m . This efficiency is directly related to the grating modulation depth by the coefficient $\beta = 2\pi\lambda^{-1}(n - 1)\Delta h$. The maximum first-order diffraction efficiency is $\eta_{\pm 1} = 0.34$, obtained for $\beta = 3.68$. The integral term $F(k_x)$ in Eq. (3), expressed as a function of the far-field coordinates, represents an envelope function that determines the overall shape and intensity distribution of each diffraction order. For a sinusoidal periodic grating, where the local grating vector magnitude $g(x)$ is constant with position, $F(k_x) = \delta(m2\pi/\Lambda - k_x)$ gives a well-defined diffraction angle for each order determined by Bragg's law. In the case of linearly chirped gratings, the local spatial frequency varies as a function of position across the surface of the grating. This variation results in a continuous spread of diffraction orders over a range of angles rather than sharp spots, resulting in a broadened diffraction pattern.

Fig. 5 (a) Schematic of the experimental setup used to evaluate the diffraction pattern of the chirped surface relief grating during the inscription process. A 633-nm probe beam is directed onto the sample and the resulting diffraction pattern is recorded using a camera. BS, beam splitter; TL, tube lens. (b) Experimentally observed diffraction pattern (top) and corresponding intensity profile (bottom). The shaded regions indicate the integration ranges used to extract the diffraction efficiency for the ± 1 diffraction orders. (c) Temporal evolution of the diffraction efficiency ($\eta_{\pm 1}$) and zero-order transmission (η_0) as a function of exposure time. The diffraction efficiency peaks at $\Delta t = 75$ s. The colored bands below the plot indicate the active wavelength during each time interval. The red line represents the 633-nm probe beam, the light blue line corresponds to the holographic inscription pattern at 491 nm, and the violet line denotes the assisting beam at 405 nm.

To evaluate and reconstruct the diffraction behavior of the chirped surface relief gratings during the inscription process on the azopolymer film, the digital lithography setup was integrated with an additional light source that serves as a diffraction probe. As shown in Fig. 5(a), the probe is a circularly polarized He–Ne laser beam with a wavelength of $\lambda = 633$ nm, which illuminates the sample orthogonally from the substrate side. The refractive index of the azopolymer material at this probe wavelength is $n = 1.696$. As the grating is inscribed on the azopolymer surface, the coherent light from the probe beam is diffracted by the evolving surface profile. This light is collected by the same microscope objective that projects the holographic intensity pattern responsible for the writing process and then propagates through the tube lens and an additional converging lens. This allows the diffraction pattern to be reconstructed by an optical Fourier transform, yielding the diffraction pattern $I(k_x)$ that would be observed in the far field.⁵⁴

Figure 5(b) shows the image of the recorded diffraction pattern of the p -chirped grating characterized in Fig. 4(b). To better understand the relationship between the grating vector components and the diffracted light, the experimental intensity profile was plotted as a function of the local grating vector $g(x)$, which can ultimately be related to the diffraction angles according to the generalized Bragg's law.

To track the formation of the azopolymer p -chirped grating in real time, the evolution of the diffraction efficiency was recorded at a rate of 20 Hz by continuously acquiring the evolving diffraction pattern throughout the inscription process, as shown in Fig. 5(c). Initially, the sample was exposed to the probe beam alone for 15 s before the structured illumination was initiated. This allowed a baseline diffraction signal to be established prior to grating formation. The diffraction efficiency, $\eta_{\pm 1}(t)$, was determined from the diffracted intensity profile by integrating the camera signal within the range from $g_2 = \pm 0.74$ to $g_1 = \pm 1.8 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, corresponding to the initial and final grating vectors imposed at the design stage. This frequency range also defines the first-order angular bandwidth of the fabricated chirped grating, which spans approximately 14 deg to 20 deg. Similarly, the zero-order trend, $\eta_0(t)$, was obtained by integrating the DC signal of the diffraction pattern. The diffraction efficiency was defined as the fraction of optical power in each integration region relative to the total optical power detected by the camera sensor. Because the surface modulation depth, Δh , increases approximately linearly with time during exposure in our configuration, the diffraction efficiency follows a Bessel-like trend as predicted by Eq. (3). Notably, the zero-order does not perfectly follow the Bessel prediction due to the presence of spurious probe light transmitted from the sample plane in our detection scheme.

The maximum efficiency in ± 1 orders was observed for a total exposure time of $\Delta t = 75$ s, which is consistent with the results of the topographic characterization showing an average modulation depth of $\Delta h = 0.53 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to $\beta = 3.66$. This optimal exposure time varies between samples, with a typical variability of ± 5 s. The dynamical and all-optical feedback, by probe light diffraction, ensures robustness to differences in material response or film quality, enabling the real-time optimization of the exposure parameters.

The consistency between diffraction behavior and surface modulation amplitude highlights the first key advantage of our all-optical lithographic configuration based on azopolymers. The dynamic photomorphing enabled by the azopolymers allows real-time characterization and precise tuning of the surface inscription process by analyzing the evolving diffraction efficiency. Figure 6(a) shows the three-dimensional AFM profile of the p -chirped grating fabricated by dynamically tuning the inscription light dose, stopping the holographic irradiation when the maximum diffraction efficiency was achieved. The inset panel of Fig. 6(a) confirms the correct inscription of all grating vectors by showing the experimentally retrieved distribution of surface spectra obtained by the Fourier transform of the AFM profile.

Figure 6(b) further details the effect on the first diffraction order pattern, where the broadened diffraction spot directly correlates with the spectral distribution of the grating vector. The shape of the diffraction order is in excellent agreement with the theoretical envelope function $F(g_x)$ calculated numerically from Eq. (3). The proposed scalar diffraction model was further validated by inscribing a q -chirped grating, which exhibits a distinct distribution of light in the first diffraction order. This second chirped grating was designed within the same periodicity range but with a key difference. Instead of a linear increase in periodicity, a linear decrease in grating vector components was imposed. The three-dimensional AFM image of the inscribed q -chirped grating (after an exposure time of $\Delta t = 75$ s) is shown in Fig. 6(c). The corresponding diffraction profile, plotted in Fig. 6(d), reveals a more uniform first-order diffraction band, in agreement with the theoretical predictions of the scalar model. This uniformity arises from the equal contribution of the grating vectors, which were intentionally designed to have equal weight. In contrast, for the p -chirped geometry, the higher magnitude grating vector components have a reduced weight, resulting in weaker diffraction at larger angles.

Fig. 6 (a), (c) Atomic force microscope three-dimensional profiles of the p -chirped and q -chirped gratings. The inset shows the surface spectral components obtained by Fourier transforming the AFM image using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm. (b) and (d) Comparison of simulated (dashed line) and experimental (solid line) first-order diffraction intensity profiles for the p -chirped and q -chirped gratings, respectively.

Beyond the first level of dynamic control, which allows tuning of the diffraction efficiency during the writing process, the intrinsic reconfigurability of the azopolymer provides a more advanced capability, enabling complete reprogramming of the surface morphology. This, in turn, allows a complete redesign of the first-order diffraction light distribution. To fully demonstrate this potential, a p -chirped grating was first inscribed and the temporal evolution of the diffraction efficiency $\eta_{+1}(t)$ was used to assess the inscription dynamics, as shown in Fig. 7(a). During exposure, the diffraction efficiency follows the expected Bessel-like trend with increasing exposure time. After reaching the maximum efficiency for the optimal exposure time Δt , as previously characterized, the holographic beam was turned off. The diffraction efficiency remains stable over time, confirming proper inscription and long-term stability of the structured surface.

To demonstrate its reconfigurability, the surface geometry was optically erased within a few seconds using the additional 405 nm at the erasing power, following the same procedure as described in our previous work.²⁴ The complete erasure of the surface morphology is confirmed by the drop of the diffraction efficiency signal. The same azopolymer area was then re-exposed to a new holographic intensity distribution, this time following a q -chirped geometry. Remarkably, maximum diffraction efficiency was again achieved within the same exposure time, illustrating the reproducibility of the reprogramming process and the negligible degradation effects of our material due to the erasing process. Further evidence of the surface reshaping is provided in Fig. 7(b), where the diffraction profile, including the zero and ± 1 orders, is plotted as a function

Fig. 7 (a) First-order diffraction efficiency curve recorded during the dynamic inscription of a reprogrammable chirped grating, transitioning from a p -chirped to a q -chirped design. The color bands below the plot indicate the active wavelength during each time interval. The red line represents the probe beam at 633 nm, the light blue line corresponds to the holographic inscription pattern at 491 nm, and the violet line denotes the assisting/erasing beam at 405 nm. (b) Temporal evolution of the diffraction pattern profile. The colormap is optimized for pattern visibility, with white regions indicating dark areas in the diffraction pattern. The colormap range has been adjusted to enhance the contrast of the diffracted orders rather than the zero-order component. (c) Diffraction pattern profiles were captured during (i) the p -chirped grating inscription, (ii) the erasure phase, and (iii) the subsequent q -chirped grating inscription.

of time. During inscription, the shape of the diffraction pattern remains largely constant, with exposure time primarily influencing the amount of diffracted light in each order. This observation is confirmed by the diffraction profile plot in Fig. 7(c), which shows the temporal evolution of the diffraction band for both the p - and q -chirped gratings shown in panels (i) and (iii), respectively. Furthermore, the diffraction behavior is tracked during the erasing process (ii), highlighting the fast surface reprogramming dynamics enabled by the azopolymer. This experiment demonstrates not only the ability to encode a wide range of grating vectors into an azopolymer surface relief grating but also the ability to fully engineer and reshape the diffraction order itself, opening up new possibilities for customized and reprogrammable light shapers fabricated as chirped azopolymer surface relief gratings.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates the fabrication of linearly chirped diffraction gratings via azopolymer-based photomorphing using digital holographic lithography. By utilizing computer-controlled intensity pattern generation, we achieved optimized structured illumination with a precisely designed distribution of grating components, minimizing mismatch deviations from the design. The optimization of the holographic beam directly translates into diffractive optical devices whose performance closely matches theoretical predictions, including those derived from a scalar diffraction model for linear chirped gratings. Experimental validation shows a first-order diffraction efficiency of $\sim 34\%$, comparable to that of binary static gratings produced using conventional lithographic techniques. Such optical performance is particularly relevant given the ability to monitor and dynamically adjust the diffraction efficiency, even in real time during fabrication, and the advantage of full optical reconfigurability of the fabricated diffraction gratings. This mechanism allows precise tuning of the inscription parameters, ensuring optimal efficiency and sample-to-sample reproducibility. Unlike the conventional materials used in standard lithographic techniques, azopolymers can be directly used as grating materials, enabling their optical functionality to be fully reprogrammed through surface relief remorphing. The process can perform multiple rewrite cycles on scales of one minute each, with an erasure time of less than 10 s. These timescales are compatible with many real-world scenarios requiring low-frequency reconfiguration, such as adaptive optics or tunable filtering applications. Although the current implementation addresses a patterning area of $\sim 150 \mu\text{m}$, the approach is inherently scalable. Larger areas can be patterned using tiling strategies, and further extension of the chirp range and grating lateral size is possible through optical system engineering as the incorporation of high-resolution SLMs and high-numerical-aperture projection optics with a wider field of view. Moreover, the digital holographic patterning technique can be adapted to produce continuously varying or step-like surface geometries, enabling further control over diffraction efficiency and angular bandwidth. This opens the door to ready-to-use or on-demand reprogrammable optical components with arbitrarily complex functionality, a feature typically unattainable with standard lithographic methods.

Disclosures

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Code and Data Availability

The data presented in this article are publicly available on Zenodo.org at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528296>.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by an ERC grant (HyperMaSH, 101164874), funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. We gratefully acknowledge the support from the University of Naples Federico II through the FRA 2022 program.

References

1. F. Hopkinson and D. Rittenhouse, "An optical problem, proposed by Mr. Hopkinson, and solved by Mr. Rittenhouse," *Trans. Am. Philos. Soc.* **2**, 201 (1786).
2. B. C. Kress and P. Meyrueis, *Applied Digital Optics: From Micro-optics to Nanophotonics*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Hoboken, NJ (2010).
3. D. C. O'Shea et al., *Diffractive Optics: Design, Fabrication, and Test*, SPIE Press, Bellingham, Washington (2004).
4. F. Reda et al., "Holographic photo-morphing of polymer surfaces for reprogrammable diffractive optics," *Proc. SPIE* **13382**, 133820N (2025).
5. C. Ranacher et al., "Design of a mid-infrared bandpass filter with large rejection bandwidth for silicon photonics," *J. Lightwave Technol.* **37**(15), 3770–3776 (2019).
6. E. Bailey and R. G. Sabat, "Surface plasmon bandwidth increase using chirped-pitch linear diffraction gratings," *Opt. Express* **25**(6), 6904 (2017).
7. E. ElShamla, S. Hekal, and L. R. Gomma, "Assessment of light diffraction and focusing of chirped gratings by the beam propagation method," *Opt. Commun.* **457**, 124621 (2020).
8. L. M. Sanchez-Brea, F. J. Torcal-Milla, and J. Buencuerpo, "Far-field diffraction of linear chirped gratings," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **107**, 337–343 (2018).
9. N. Gao et al., "Quasi-periodic gratings: diffraction orders accelerate along curves," *Opt. Lett.* **38**(15), 2829 (2013).
10. S. Nezhadbadeh et al., "Chirped-grating spectrometer-on-a-chip," *Opt. Express* **28**(17), 24501 (2020).
11. Y.-J. Hung et al., "Optical spectrometer based on continuously-chirped guided mode resonance filter," *Opt. Express* **26**(21), 27515 (2018).
12. G. Fortin and N. McCarthy, "Chirped holographic grating used as the dispersive element in an optical spectrometer," *Appl. Opt.* **44**(23), 4874 (2005).
13. Y. Wang et al., "The development progress of surface structure diffraction gratings: from manufacturing technology to spectroscopic applications," *Appl. Sci.* **12**(13), 6503 (2022).
14. J. Gao et al., "A review on fabrication of blazed gratings," *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **54**(31), 313001 (2021).
15. S. Hatefi and K. Abou-El-Hossein, "Review of single-point diamond turning process in terms of ultra-precision optical surface roughness," *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* **106**(5–6), 2167–2187 (2020).
16. Y. Shimizu, "Laser interference lithography for fabrication of planar scale gratings for optical metrology," *Nanomanuf. Metrol.* **4**(1), 3–27 (2021).
17. E. Sharma et al., "Evolution in lithography techniques: microlithography to nanolithography," *Nanomaterials* **12**(16), 2754 (2022).
18. K. Kim et al., "Light-directed soft mass migration for micro/nanophotonics," *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **7**(16), 1900074 (2019).
19. A. Priimagi and A. Shevchenko, "Azopolymer-based micro- and nanopatterning for photonic applications," *J. Polym. Sci. B Polym. Phys.* **52**(3), 163–182 (2014).
20. S. L. Oscurato et al., "From nanoscopic to macroscopic photo-driven motion in azobenzene-containing materials," *Nanophotonics* **7**(8), 1387–1422 (2018).
21. B. Yadav et al., "Orientation approach to directional photodeformations in glassy side-chain azopolymers," *J. Phys. Chem. B* **123**(15), 3337–3347 (2019).
22. N. Tverdokhleba et al., "Viscoplastic modeling of surface relief grating growth on isotropic and preoriented azopolymer films," *Polymers* **15**(2), 463 (2023).
23. M. Saphiannikova, V. Toshchevikov, and N. Tverdokhleba, "Optical deformations of azobenzene polymers: orientation approach vs. other concepts," *Soft Matter* **20**(12), 2688–2710 (2024).
24. S. L. Oscurato et al., "Shapeshifting diffractive optical devices," *Laser Photonics Rev.* **16**(4), 2100514 (2022).
25. J. Vapaavuori et al., "From partial to complete optical erasure of azobenzene-polymer gratings: effect of molecular weight," *J. Mater. Chem. C* **3**(42), 11011–11016 (2015).
26. J. Krüger et al., "Optical reconfiguration of surface relief gratings on supramolecular polymer films using grating translation and superposition," *J. Appl. Phys.* **125**(24), 243108 (2019).
27. N. S. Yadavalli, M. Saphiannikova, and S. Santer, "Photosensitive response of azobenzene containing films towards pure intensity or polarization interference patterns," *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **105**(5), 051601 (2014).
28. J. Jelken, C. Henkel, and S. Santer, "Formation of half-period surface relief gratings in azobenzene containing polymer films," *Appl. Phys. B* **126**(9), 149 (2020).
29. A. Kozanecka-Szmigiel et al., "Surface relief modulated grating in Azo polymer—from the tailoring of diffraction order to reshaping of a laser beam," *Materials* **15**(22), 8088 (2022).
30. S. Moujdi et al., "Surface relief gratings in Azo-polymers revisited," *J. Appl. Phys.* **124**(21), 213103 (2018).
31. Y. Lim, B. Kang, and S. Lee, "Photo-transformable gratings for augmented reality," *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **31**(28), 2100839 (2021).
32. L. Nedelchev et al., "Tunable polarization and surface relief holographic gratings in azopolymer nanocomposites with incorporated goethite (α -FeOOH) nanorods," *Photonics* **8**(8), 306 (2021).

33. S. L. Oscurato et al., “Large-scale multiplexed azopolymer gratings with engineered diffraction behavior,” *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **8**(21), 2101375 (2021).
34. M. Salvatore, F. Borbone, and S. L. Oscurato, “Deterministic realization of quasicrystal surface relief gratings on thin azopolymer films,” *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **7**(11), 1902118 (2020).
35. H. Rekola et al., “Digital holographic microscopy for real-time observation of surface-relief grating formation on azobenzene-containing films,” *Sci. Rep.* **10**(1), 19642 (2020).
36. A. Berdin, H. T. Rekola, and A. Priimagi, “Complex Fourier surfaces by superposition of multiple gratings on azobenzene thin films,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **12**(4), 2301597 (2024).
37. J. Leibold and R. G. Sabat, “Laser-induced controllable chirped-pitch circular surface-relief diffraction gratings on AZO glass,” *Photonics Res.* **3**(4), 158 (2015).
38. S. L. Oscurato et al., “Computer-generated holograms for complex surface reliefs on azopolymer films,” *Sci. Rep.* **9**(1), 6775 (2019).
39. J. Strobelt et al., “Supramolecular azopolymers for dynamic surface microstructures using digital polarization optics,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **11**(8), 2202245 (2023).
40. Y. Lim et al., “Fourier surfaces reaching full-color diffraction limits,” *Adv. Mater.* **36**(40), 2404540 (2024).
41. O. Senel et al., “Continuous laser printing of surface relief gratings on azopolymer films,” *Opt. Express* **32**(26), 47385 (2024).
42. M. Salvatore et al., “Multilevel azopolymer patterning from digital holographic lithography,” *RSC Appl. Interfaces* **2**, 56–60 (2025).
43. I. K. Januariyasa et al., “Molding three-dimensional azopolymer microstructures with holographically structured light,” *RSC Appl. Interfaces* **1**(6), 1198–1207 (2024).
44. F. Reda et al., “Reprogrammable holograms from maskless surface photomorphing,” *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **11**(21), 2300823 (2023).
45. J. Strobelt et al., “Optical microstructure fabrication using structured polarized illumination,” *Opt. Express* **30**(5), 7308 (2022).
46. F. Reda et al., “Varifocal diffractive lenses for multi-depth microscope imaging,” *Opt. Express* **30**(8), 12695 (2022).
47. F. Reda et al., “Accurate morphology-related diffraction behavior of light-induced surface relief gratings on azopolymers,” *ACS Mater. Lett.* **4**(5), 953–959 (2022).
48. M. Salvatore et al., “Diffractive refractometer based on scalar theory,” *Polymers* **15**(7), 1605 (2023).
49. J. Goodman, *Introduction to Fourier Optics*, 4th ed., W. H. Freeman, New York (2017).
50. N. Lassaline et al., “Optical Fourier surfaces,” *Nature* **582**(7813), 506–510 (2020).
51. M. Pasienski and B. DeMarco, “A high-accuracy algorithm for designing arbitrary holographic atom traps,” *Opt. Express* **16**(3), 2176 (2008).
52. L. Novotny and B. Hecht, *Principles of Nano-Optics*, 2nd ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge (2012).
53. G. N. Watson, *A Treatise on the Theory of Bessel Functions*, Cambridge University Press (1995).
54. F. Reda et al., “Shape retrieval of azopolymer surface relief gratings from diffraction efficiency measurement,” *ACS Appl. Opt. Mater.* **3**(1), 6–13 (2024).

Francesco Reda received his PhD in quantum technologies in 2024 from the University of Naples Federico II, with a dissertation on reprogrammable flat optics using maskless photomorphing of azopolymers. Since then, he has been working as a postdoctoral researcher at the same institution, developing holographic techniques for the fabrication of functionalized surfaces.

Fabio Borbone is an associate professor at the University of Naples Federico II. He is a materials chemist whose research interests include the development of advanced materials for photonics, electro-optics, optoelectronics and sensors, with a focus on the design of photoresponsive materials (azomaterials, photopolymers) for photopatterning and surface structuring.

Marcella Salvatore is an assistant professor at the University of Naples Federico II. She is a materials engineer whose research focuses on azomaterials surface patterning and tuning of the surface functionality. Specifically, she is interested in developing innovative surface designs for applications such as wettability control and optical devices.

Stefano L. Oscurato is an associate professor at the University of Naples Federico II, where he leads the Holographic Lithography research group. His research focuses on the vectorial light-induced structuring of photosensitive materials using computer-generated holograms. He collaborates closely with several world-leading groups in nanophotonics, photosensitive materials, and advanced lithography. In 2024, he was awarded an ERC Starting Grant.